

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The commonest is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or gentle brown (cinnamon), generally even white. Not all the time black in coloration. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear may be found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such because the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to 6 ft in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, however their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of one of the best at climbing bushes. Their comparatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb trees for safety, food, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their weight loss plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Eating regimen: Their assorted weight loss plan provides them the flexibility to live in a large vary of habitats. They also eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the probably bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are responsible for nearly all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per year. Although their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and lowered habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large construct, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the information, which led to the name of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals reminiscent of elk and moose. Their coloration varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet lengthy, and have a shoulder top of 3. Three feet. □□ Diet: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been recognized to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies tend to be bigger than those discovered within the Rocky Mountains because of a richer weight loss plan. Each year there are forty six assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for his or her aggressive behavior, grizzlies are accountable for the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are almost as giant as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1, four hundred pounds, eight feet lengthy, and four feet tall on the shoulder. □□ Weight loss plan: Their food regimen is similar to mainland grizzly bears. However, attributable to extra plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to grow to be their very own subspecies. This has led to a extra complicated social construction which results in less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. Because of their isolation, there is just one assault on people each different 12 months. Largest species of bear on the earth weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Diet is mostly made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range in the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and could be 7 to 10 toes tall. They're a threatened species on account of lack of habitat from local weather change. Despite their huge measurement polar bears can be quick, maintaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Options: In comparison with different bears, polar bears have a slimmer physique, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Food regimen: Their food plan consists mostly of animals, particularly seals which they will scent from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears will be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are rare due to the remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream shade chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Easy to tame and infrequently widespread in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands throughout Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered vulnerable. □□ Dimension: One of many smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand 47 to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight loss plan: Depending on the season it generally feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and

honey. Attacks on people are rising as individuals encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Dangerous? They are one among the best bears to tame (and therefore widespread in circuses), but Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered solely in China. 99% of its food plan is bamboo. In actual fact, the second person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas defending his sheep. Known for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. ☐☐ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 remain in the wild and they're thought of a susceptible species. ☐☐ Size: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and could be over four ft tall, a powerful feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at delivery. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same sample in gentle brown and white. ☐☐ Food plan: In contrast to different bears the panda's food regimen is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Features: The giant panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over forty times a day! ☐☐ Harmful? Attacks are uncommon but dangerous, on condition that pandas have one among the very best bite forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐ Location: The Solar bear is discovered in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however thought of vulnerable and on the decline resulting from loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different physique parts utilized in conventional medicines. ☐☐ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Options: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that appears like a rising solar. In addition they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Eating regimen: Solar bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In reality, they've an extremely lengthy tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Harmful? Because of its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐ Location: The Sloth bear is discovered in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of lower than 20,000, they are thought of susceptible. ☐☐ Size: They are 55 to seventy five inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Features: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to inform other than different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they are very quick and might out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their massive curved claws. ☐☐ Food plan: Their food plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Dangerous? They are one of the vital aggressive bears, with the most assaults on people, largely on account of shock encounters. They blow the dust around with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and don't combine well with rhinos and elephants, usually charging at each other when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last quick-confronted bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that appear like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to seventy nine inches tall. ☐☐ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final brief-confronted bear and the only bear native to South America. ☐☐ Options: The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that typically look like glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Weight-reduction plan: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a weight loss plan consisting of [bts with teddy bear](#) mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Dangerous? Living in remote mountains, these shy bears often is the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is closer to the polar bear. They function the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, however have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA assessments have been unable to determine what type of bear it was. Adorable koalas should not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in space. Most bear attacks happen when a bear is startled or defending their cubs. Pink pandas? They're in their very own family which can be closer cousins with skunks and

raccoons than bears. 1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that may point out a bear is close by, wherein case you need to be extra vigilant. Listed here are a number of ideas you can use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you may have nice intentions, a bear is likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** In case you see a bear, do not attempt to method or feed it. This includes meals, but in addition your toiletries, for example. Whichever method you choose, be sure it's at the least 200 toes away from your tent so you do not attract bears to your campsite. 4. **Keep CALM.** In case you meet a bear, do not run. Try to make yourself look as massive as potential, waving your arms above your head. You can even lengthen a jacket above your head to make your self look larger. Lock these items in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Do not scream or try to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Speak to it calmly and slowly back away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Struggle Again.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play useless. Which bear is the most important? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.Zero to 8.4 feet long, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the largest bear by each dimension and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Battle again with all your power and hope that it's going to back down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for the most attacks. When in bear nation, it's all the time wise to hold bear spray. It's properly deserved, especially when cubs are around. Annually there are roughly 46 grizzly attacks, 6 resulting in dying. In North America, grizzly bears have essentially the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one assault per yr. When it comes to raw chunk power, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's bite reigns supreme. All bears are strong and not to be messed with. When using the bite power quotient (chunk energy relative to dimension), the solar bear packs essentially the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he became an icon and to today is the star of the longest-working public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous thru-hikers to try to master the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, although he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a duty-free lifestyle. He additionally could be the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would go to on the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the town in Canada close to where he was from. Chris additionally wrote Find out how to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After thru-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and how-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

